

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MWCNTS/PVA COMPOSITE HYDROGELS WITH HIGH MECHANICAL AND ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTY FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATION

Kun Qiao¹, Yudong Zheng^{1*}, Wei Li¹, Yanyi Huang¹, Lingling Ren²

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Science and Technology Beijing, Beijing 100083, PR China. ² National Institute of Metrology of China, Beijing, 100013, PR China

* Corresponding author: Yudong Zheng (zhengyudong@mater.ustb.edu.cn)

Keywords: *Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes, Polyvinyl Alcohol, Composite Hydrogel, Electrophoretic deposition, Mechanical properties,*

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) show unique mechanical, electrical and thermal properties and large surface area as well as the potential for surface functionalization and they have been used in applications of biosensors and considered as potential reinforcement materials in biocomposites for a long time^[1-7]. But one of concerns about toxicity effects of CNT is their risk in the body environment, such as inflammatory responses or the formation of Granuloma^[8]. To avoid this, we combine with CNTs Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogel molecules.

PVA is a useful water-soluble synthetic hydrogel, which has been widely studied and applied in the form of fiber, film and gel^[9-11]. PVA hydrogel has been advanced as a biomaterial for the applications of medical devices because of its viscoelastic nature, high water content, non-toxic and biocompatibility^[12,13]. Compare to other hydrogel molecules, PVA-H is easier to get crosslinked without the addition of chemical crosslinking agents, which may be devastating when released into the body system. After a freezing-thawing process, PVA molecular chains are cross-linked by entanglement, molecular association, or crystallites^[14,15].

Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) has attracted substantial attention for the fabrication of thin films and coatings of polymers^[16], carbon nanotubes (CNTs)^[17,18] and composite materials^[19-21] for the surface modification. Compare to other methods, EPD offers the advantage of a high deposition rate and the possibility of the fabrication of relatively thick coatings^[22,23].

In the recent years, the kinetics of EPD has not been probed and how the factors like voltage and time influencing the process of deposition is still indefinite. Though some encouraging moderate improvement of tensile strength and modulus, the overall mechanical properties of the hydrogels

produced were still low. Systematical study on carbon nanotubes reinforced PVA in hydrogel form in order to explore its full potential as multifunctional biomaterial has yet to be done.

Our study aims develop another successful way to disperse MWCNTs within PVA aqueous solution by functionalizing the nanotubes with strong oxidant and co-deposit them on the surface of bare copper electrode under direct current to form a uniform coating and analyzing influence of different parameters on EPD process. Then develop a high-performance MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogel for biomedical applications.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

MWCNTs (diameter~40 - 60 nm, length~1 - 2 μ m, amorphous <3%) were purchased from Shenzhen Nanotech Port Co. Ltd. in China and used as received. Polyvinyl alcohol powders (polymerization degree of ~1750 and 99% hydrolyzed) were supplied by Beijing Xisi Chemicals Co.Ltd. The surfactants investigated were Poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP, K-30 with the average molecular weight of 40,000) (Yily Fine Chemicals Co.Ltd., Beijing, China). And used as received to prepare 0.5wt.% aqueous solutions. $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ was supplied by Beijing Chemical Works. Water was distilled and deionized.

2.2 Preparation and Characterization of MWCNTS/PVA Modified Electrodes

MWCNTs was subjected to ultrasonic wave in H_2O_2 , and refluxed for a while. Then the aggregates were obtained by a mild centrifugation (CF). MWCNTs aggregates were treated at elevated temperature and prepared by chemical oxidation in a concentrated acid. Once cooling, the oxidized MWCNTs were washed to neutral with distilled water. MWCNTs after oxidization were mixed with distill water

(1mg/mL) and subjected to ultrasonic wave for hours. In order to obtain the MWCNTs/PVA dispersion, put PVA into the MWCNTs aqueous solution and heat up for 1.5h. EPD was implemented using a DC power supply under a range of conditions, including variation of electric field strength (10-35 V/cm) and deposition time (0.5-3.5min), to investigate the kinetics of the deposition process and the optimal condition. Then the MWCNTs/PVA coated electrode was placed into a refrigerator for 10 h and then it was allowed to thaw at room temperature for 4 h and repeated the whole process for four times.

The surface morphology of MWCNTs/PVA modified electrodes was characterized by field emission gun-scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, Apollo 300, and 10 KV). Cyclic voltammetry was performed using the electrochemical workstation CH instrument 618D with a conventional three-electrode system, a working electrode, a platinum plate (20 mm*20 mm*0.3 mm) as counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. The chemical composition of the PBS solution is $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10.5 g/L) and KH_2PO_4 (2.6 g/L).

2.3 Preparation and Characterization of MWCNT/PVA Composite Hydrogel

A stable aqueous MWCNT dispersion was obtained by using nonionic surfactant PVP with the optimized PVP/MWCNT weight ratio of 20% from the above dispersions investigated. Thus, a series of MWCNT-PVP dispersions were made by adding MWCNTs (0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 wt%, respectively) into aqueous PVP solutions with a fixed weight ratio of PVP/MWCNT 20% in the following MWCNT/PVA hydrogel preparation. In all experiments, the continuous matrix of PVA hydrogel was made from 25 wt% PVA aqueous solution. MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogel was prepared by freezing-thawing technique from a mixture of the MWCNT-PVP dispersion and PVA. The MWCNT-PVP dispersion was sonicated (200W) for 15 min at room temperature. Then PVA powder was added into the uniform MWCNT-PVP dispersion, and the mixture was stirred and heated up to 120 °C in a YX-280 pressure steam sterilizer (Binjiang Medical Equipment Ltd., Jiangsu, China) and maintained at 120 °C (0.1 MPa) for 1.5 h. After mixing, the hot

mixture was slowly decanted into a mold and settled for a few minutes to release the air bubbles trapped in the mixture. Finally, the mixture was placed into a refrigerator and kept at 26 °C for 10h and then it was allowed to thaw at room temperature for 4 h. After these freezing-thawing cycles for four times, a composite hydrogel was generated. For comparison, PVA hydrogel, PVA-PVP hydrogel (PVP:PVA ratio 0.2 wt%) and MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogel in absence of PVP (1.0 wt% MWCNTs) were also prepared in the same way.

Tensile stress-strain properties and tear strength were determined using a Chaoyang WDS-5 universal mechanical tester with the loading rate kept at a strain rate of 500 mm/min at room temperature. The mechanical testing specimens were casted directly in the mold through the casting procedures described above, with the specimen dimensions following ISO standards. The tensile specimen was dumb-bell shape with width 4 mm, thickness 2 mm and gauge length 20 mm [ISO 37:2005(E)] In each case, five samples were tested from which the mean and standard deviation were calculated. The friction coefficient was obtained by the ball disk sliding friction experiments (10 N load force, 100 r/min speed of rotation) using an UMT-2 universal micro-tribometer tester (Center of Tribology company, US) with deionized water as lubricant.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Effects on Deposit Yield and Electrochemical Performance

The deposit yield (deposit weight per surface area) was measured at different voltage (10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35V) and constant time (1 min). The deposit yield versus applied voltage (Y-V) curve in Fig. 1 shows as the electric-field strength increases (the distance between electrodes are fixed), the movement of MWCNTs/PVA is faster.

Fig.1. Deposit yield versus applied voltage for compo-site film prepared for 1 min from MWCNTs/PVA dispersions (electrode separation=1cm).

It could also be manifested in Fig.2 that the higher voltage, the more MWCNTs/PVA composite nanoparticles deposited on the substrate. The relationship between MWCNTs/PVA deposition yield and voltage for EPD matches the results observed by other researchers [24, 25]. The surface morphology of different kinds of MWCNTs/PVA modified electrodes corresponding to varied applied potentials is also shown. It is evident that as the voltage becomes higher, the amount of MWCNTs/PVA increases accordingly, and the deposition film tends to uniform and even. But for higher voltage, more and more bubbles were found near the surface of two electrodes as the electrolysis of water, and it is difficult to get uniform deposition.

Fig.2. Optical photographs and Surface morphology of MWCNTs/PVA composite coating obtained by EPD at the voltages of (a)10V,(b)20V,(c)35V,

Cyclic voltammograms obtained with different voltages of deposition in phosphate buffered solution (PBS) containing 1mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ at a scan rate of 10mv/s are shown in Fig.3 and from the CV curve a capacitance value could be generated, which can be characterized by integrating the areas under the curves. The anodic and cathodic peak currents increase with increasing the voltage of EPD process. As more and more MWCNTs/PVA particles deposited on the substrate, the charge exchange rate on the surface of electrode is improved, and it explains why the current becomes higher with increasing voltage.

Fig.3. CV curves of 1 mM Fe(CN)₆³⁻ in PBS for MWCNTs/PVA EPD processed electrodes at different applied voltages. The accumulation time and scan rate is 2s and 10mv/s, respectively

The variation of deposit yield (Y) versus time (t) for deposition voltages of 35 V is shown in Fig. 4. From 0.5 min to 2.5 min, the deposit yield increases with extending the time, and the tendency is matched with the theory. But as time prolonged, the phenomenon of electrolysis of water is also notable, and the bubbles near the surface of two electrodes affect the deposition process and then the deposit yield would not increase for longer time. So the deposition time should be limited within 2.5 min.

Fig.4. Deposit yield versus deposition time for composite film prepared at a deposition voltage of 35 v.

The surface morphology of deposits in Fig. 5 may also prove this trend. Relationship between MWCNTs/PVA deposition yield and time for EPD is also verified by other researchers [26, 27]. It is shown that MWCNTs/PVA-modified electrodes corresponding to varied applied time from time 0.5min to 2.5min, the deposit density increases and the film

becomes even; for 3.5min deposition, there are notable micropores.

Fig.5. Surface morphology of composite film obtained by EPD for different deposition time (a) for 0.5min, (b) for 1.5min, (c) for 2.5min, and (d) for 3.5min.

Cyclic voltammograms obtained with different time of deposition in PBS containing 1mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ at a scan rate of 10mv/s are shown in Fig.6. The anodic and cathodic peak currents increase with increasing the time of EPD process from 0.5min to 3min, but decrease for 3.5 min of deposition. This phenomenon is corresponding to the deposit yield vs. time curve and surface morphology of the electrodes. The more MWCNTs/PVA deposited on the electrode, the more active sites on modified electrode, and the response to the electron transfer is more sensitive. That explains the peak current increase with extending the time.

Fig.6. CV curves of 1 mM $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ in PBS for MWCNTs/PVA EPD processed electrodes for different deposition time. The accumulation time and scan rate is 2s and 10mv/s, respectively.

3.2 Comparison between Modified Electrode and Bare Copper Electrode

The cyclic voltammograms obtained in phosphate buffered solution (PBS) containing 1mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ at bare copper electrode and MWCNTs/PVA modified electrode at a scan rate of 10mv/s are shown in Fig.7 (a) that the redox peaks current: modified electrode > bare Cu. Oxidation and reduction peaks are observed at 0.643v and 0.566v at bare copper electrode, 0.624v and 0.542v at modified electrode. The peak-to-peak separation on copper is 77 mv, which is relatively close to the value obtained according to the theory and function. The peak to peak separation of MWCNTs/PVA modified electrodes is 82 mv and is slightly larger than copper which can be explained with the PVA film acting as a barrier against the $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ to reach the electrode surface, but the peaks current is much higher. This can be attributed to the larger electroactive surface area at the MWCNTs/PVA coating after the inclusion of MWCNTs in PVA matrices. It means due to the modification of MWCNTs, there are more active sites on the surface of the modified electrode, and the response to the electron transfer is more sensitive.

Fig.7 (a) Cyclic voltammetry responses of 1 mM Fe (CN)₆³⁻ in PBS at bare copper electrode and MWCNTs/PVA modified electrode. (b) Cyclic voltammograms at MWCNTs/PVA modified electrode in PBS containing 1 mM Fe (CN)₆³⁻ at different scan rate. (c) The relationship between peak currents and scan rate.

Cyclic voltammograms obtained with different scan rates in aqueous PBS containing 1mM Fe (CN)₆³⁻ at MWCNTs/PVA modified electrode are shown in Fig.7(b). The anodic and cathodic peak currents increase with increasing the potential scan rate ranging from 10mV/s to 100mV/s. The detailed description of the relationship between peak currents and scan rate is shown in the insert of Fig.7(c). The anodic and cathodic peak current vs. square root of the scan rate is linear, which suggests that the process is predominantly diffusion controlled and manifests this type of modified electrode is much better when compared to bare copper electrode.

3.3 Mechanical Properties of MWCNT/PVA Composite Hydrogels

Tensile test was performed to evaluate the effect of carbon nanotubes on the mechanical properties of the MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogels. Fig.8(a) shows the typical tensile behavior of PVA hydrogel and MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogels. In each case of the tensile tests, the samples were broken in the linear elastic region without obvious yield phenomenon and further plastic deformation Fig.8(a), showing a characteristic feature of brittle fracture. Despite their brittle fracture behavior, the hydrogels performed rubber-like large-strain flexibility with the elongation-at-break values between 110% and 180%. The moduli of composite hydrogels determined by the slope of stress-strain curves were all higher than that of PVA hydrogel itself.

Fig.8. (a) Tensile stress-strain curves of (1) PVA hydrogel and MWCNT/PVA hydrogels with different MWCNT contents (b) Comparison of tear strength of the composite hydrogels with different MWCNT contents.

Similar to the trend of the tensile strength and elongation-at-break as a function of the MWCNT content, the tear strength of PVA hydrogel matrix is drastically enhanced by adding a small amount of PVP-wrapped MWCNTs, but the improvement decreases with a further increase of the MWCNT content, as presented in Fig.8(b). MWCNT/PVA hydrogel with 1.0 wt% carbon nanotubes has the highest tear strength of 9.1 kN/m, a 63% improvement over PVA hydrogel. However, the value decreases to 7.2 kN/m when the MWCNT content is increased to 2.0 wt%.

There are a number of physical parameters of determining the mechanical properties of a polymeric hydrogel, such as the density, molecular weight, and crosslinking degree of the network for either chemical or physical crosslinked polymers, porosity of the polymeric network etc [12, 13, 28, 29]. For MWCNT/PVA composite based hydrogels, we believe that the porosity of the network, the uniformity of composite and the strong interfacial

interaction between PVP-wrapped MWCNTs and PVA hydrogel matrix have a significant effect on their mechanical properties.

3.4 Tribological Properties of MWCNT/PVA Hydrogels

Fig.9(a) shows representative COF curves of PVA hydrogel and composite hydrogels measured by the ball-disk sliding friction experiments. The COF value of each sample was obtained by averaging the reading of load application over 40 sec from the plateau of the COF curve. As illustrated in Fig.9(b), the COF value of PVA hydrogel decreases clearly from 0.248 to 0.203 in the presence of a small amount of PVP (0.2 wt%). Detail study on the reduction of COF of PVA by blending with PVP was reported in^[30]. Interestingly, the COF values of all MWCNT/PVA hydrogels developed are also lower than PVA hydrogel similar to PVA-PVP blend hydrogel (0.204) regardless of the amount of MWCNTs. In contrast, MWCNT/PVA hydrogel in the absence of PVP has the highest COF value of 0.282 in Fig.9(b). Those results imply that the tribological properties of the hydrogels are predominated by the nature of polymer hydrogels and interface between polymer matrix and nanotubes. Clearly, PVP surfactant is attributed to the significant improvement of tribological properties for PVA hydrogel. It is suggested that PVP probably smoothes the material surface and thus screens PVA and MWCNTs. In a microporous three-dimensional network structure of PVA hydrogel, the water which contributed to the lubrication between the friction pair was gradually squeezed out from the pores of the three-dimensional polymer network. It was believed that the surface water was consisted of equilibrium water and free water^[31]. Equilibrium water played a major role during the lubrication process rather than free water because it had stronger interaction with polymer chains throughout the whole network. Amide groups from PVP chains could induce more equilibrium water and improve the wear resistance of PVA hydrogel^[12], resulting in smaller friction coefficient of PVA-PVP blends and PVP-wrapped MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogels.

Fig.9. Tribological properties of hydrogels. (a) Representative coefficient of friction (COF) curves for (1) PVA hydrogel, (2) MWCNT(0.5 wt%)-PVP/PVA hydrogel and (3)MWCNT(2.0 wt%)-PVP/PVA hydrogel. (b) Comparison of COF values of different MWCNT/PVA hydrogel

3 Conclusion

The effect of main EPD parameters including applied voltage and deposition time on the deposit yield as well as electrochemical performance of modified electrode was investigated. The deposit yield increased by increasing applied voltage (below 35v) and deposit time (below 2.5min). This relationship was in good agreement with EPD theoretical relations considered for ceramic powders. The more MWCNTs/PVA deposited on the electrode, the more active sites on modified electrode, and the faster response to the electron transfer. By altering the parameters of deposition, different electrochemical properties were obtained. The optimized voltage and deposit time for EPD of MWCNTs/PVA composite hydrogel coating were found to be 35v and 2.5min. Based on the optimized process parameters, the novel MWCNTs /PVA modified electrode outperform bare copper electrode and the response to the electron transfer is more sensitive. Both anodic and cathodic peak currents of

Fe (CN)₆⁴⁻/ Fe (CN)₆³⁻ redox system on modified electrode exceed those on bare copper electrode, which means there are more active sites on the surface of the modified electrode, and the response to the electron transfer is more sensitive when compared to bare copper electrode.

The reinforcement of the PVP-wrapped MWCNTs dramatically improved the mechanical properties of PVA hydrogel, depending on the concentration and distribution of carbon nanotubes. Particularly, a 133% improvement of the tensile strength and a 63% improvement of the tear strength were achieved by the addition of only 1.0 wt% of MWCNTs. In addition, all the MWCNT/PVA composite hydrogels became more wear-resistant in the presence of PVP with different MWCNT contents.

The optimized method of composite coating and the enhanced mechanical and Tribological proper-ties, in combination with their electrical /thermal conductivity and biocompatibility, will further broaden the applications. These MWCNT/PVA hydrogels are promising multifunctional materials for a wide range of biomedical applications including biosensor, artificial cartilage substitute, drug delivery and so on.

4 References

- [1] J.J. Gooding, R. Wibowo, Liu, W. Yang, D. Losic, S. Orbons, F.J. Mearns, J.G. Shapter and D.B.Hibbert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 125 (2003) 9006.
- [2] F. Patolsky, Y. Weizmann and I. Willner, *Angew. Chem. Int. Edit.*, 43 (2004) 2113.
- [3] J. Rusling, X. Yu, B. Munge, V. Patel, G. Jensen, A. Bhirde, J. Gong, S. Kim, S. Gutkind and F.Papadimitrakopoulos, *ECS Meeting Abstracts*, 602 (2006) 716.
- [4] Wakamatsu N, Takamori H, Fujigaya T, Nakashima N. *Adv Funct Mater* 2009;19(2):311-6.
- [5] Huang H, Liu CH, Wu Y, Fan S. *Adv Mater* 2005;17(13):1652-6.
- [6] Ma YJ, Yao XF, Zheng QS, Yin YJ, Jiang DJ, et al. *Appl Phys Lett* 2010;97:061909-1-9-3.
- [7] Al-Saleh MH, Sundararaj U. *Carbon* 2009;47(1):2-22.
- [8] P.A. Tran, L. Zhang and T.J. Webster, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.*, 61 (2009) 1097.
- [9] A. Peled, E. Zaguri and G. Marom, *Compos. Part A- Appl S.*, 39 (2008) 930.
- [10] A. Nilasaroya, L.A. Poole-Warren, J.M. Whitelock and P. Jo Martens, *Biomaterials*, 29 (2008) 4658.
- [11] M.L. Minus, H.G. Chae and S. Kumar, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.*, 210 (2009) 1799.
- [12] Ma R, Xiong D, Miao F, Zhang J, Peng Y. *Mat Sci Eng C* 2009;29(6):1979-83.
- [13] Bodugoz-Senturk H, Macias CE, Kung JH, Muratoglu OK. *Biomaterials* 2009;30(4):589-96.
- [14] Y.-C. Tsai and J.-D. Huang, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 8 (2006) 956.
- [15] K.Y. Lee and D.J. Mooney, *ChemInform*, 32 (2001) no.
- [16] C. Wang, J. Ma and W. Cheng, *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 173 (2003) 271.
- [17] A.R. Gardeshzadeh and B. Raissi, *Prog. Color Colorants Coat.*, 4 (2011) 51.
- [18] H. Ogiwara, M. Fukasawa and T. Saji, *Carbon*, 49 (2011) 4604.
- [19] C. Kaya, I. Singh and A.R. Boccaccini, *Adv. Eng. Mater.*, 10 (2008) 131.
- [20] K. Wu, P. Imin, Y. Sun, X. Pang, A. Adronov and I. Zhitomirsky, *Mater. Lett.*, 67 (2012) 248.
- [21] Y. Wang, I. Deen and I. Zhitomirsky, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 362 (2011) 367.
- [22] F. Sun and I. Zhitomirsky, *Surf. Eng.*, 25 (2009) 621.
- [23] M. Cheong and I. Zhitomirsky, *Colloid. Surface. A.*, 328 (2008) 73.
- [24] I. Zhitomirsky, *Sci Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 97 (2002) 279.
- [25] J. Cho, K. Konopka, K. Rozniatowski, E. Garcia-Lecina, M.S.P. Shaffer and A.R. Boccaccini, *Carbon*, 47 (2009) 58.
- [26] L. Besra and M. Liu, *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, 52 (2007) 1.
- [27] L. Besra, T. Uchikoshi, T.S. Suzuki and Y. Sakka, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 29 (2009) 1837.
- [28] Yanagioka M, Frank CW. *Langmuir* 2009, 25(10):5927-39.
- [29] Cadek M, Coleman JN, Barron V, Hedicke K, Blau WJ. *Appl Phys Lett* 2002;81(27):5123-5.
- [30] Zheng Y, Huang X, Wang Y, Xu H, Chen X., *J Appl Poly Sci* 2009;113(2):736-41.
- [31] Yasunari I, Ken-ichi H, Tadashi S., *Wear* 2005; 261(5-6):500-4.

5 Acknowledgments

This study is financially supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China Project (Grant No.51073024 and Grant No. 51273021), and the National Science and Technology Support Project of China (Grant No.2011BAK15B04).